

Fostering Innovation, Integration and Inclusion Through
Interdisciplinary Practices in Management

Digital Marketing: A Review

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ABSTRACT

Digital marketing is the marketing of products or services using digital technologies, mainly on the Internet, but also including mobile phones, display advertising, and any other digital medium. Digital marketing's development since the 1990s and 2000s has changed the way brands and businesses use technology for marketing. As digital platforms are increasingly incorporated into marketing plans and everyday life, and as people use digital devices instead of visiting physical shops, digital marketing campaigns are becoming more prevalent and efficient. This paper mainly focuses on conceptual understanding of digital marketing, how digital marketing helps today's business and some cases in the form of examples.

KEYWORDS: media, key performance indicators, mail, search engines, consumers

INTRODUCTION

I. What is Digital Marketing?

Digital marketing encompasses all marketing efforts that use an electronic device or internet. Businesses leverage digital channels such as search engines, social media, email and their websites to connect with current and prospective customers. This can also be referred as 'online marketing', 'internet marketing' or 'web marketing'. Digital marketing is defined by use of numerous digital tactics and channels to connect with customers where they spend much of their time: online. From website to business's online branding assets - digital advertising, email marketing, online brochures, and beyond -- there's spectrum of tactics falling under the umbrella of "digital marketing."

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Digital marketing methods such as Search Engine Optimization (SEO), Search Engine Marketing (SEM), Content Marketing, influencer marketing, content automation, campaign marketing, data-driven marketing, e-commerce marketing, social media marketing, social media optimization, e-mail direct marketing, display advertising, e-books, and optical disks and games are becoming more common in advancing technology. Digital marketing now extends to non-Internet channels that provide digital media, such as mobile phones (SMS and MMS), callback, and on-hold mobile ring tones.

II. A shift of Marketing from Traditional to Digital:

The development of digital marketing is inseparable from technology development. In 1971, Ray Tomlinson sent first email and his technology set the platform to allow people to send and receive files through different machines. In the

1980s, storage capacity of computer was already big enough to store huge volumes of customer information. Companies started choosing online techniques, such as database marketing, rather than limited list broker. This kind of databases allowed companies to track customers' information more effectively, thus transforming relationship between buyer and seller. However, the manual process was not so efficient.

In the 1990s, the term Digital Marketing was first coined, with debut of server/client architecture and the popularity of personal computers, the Customer Relationship Management (CRM) applications became significant part of marketing technology. Fierce competition forced vendors to include more service into their software, for example, marketing, sales and service applications. Marketers were also able to own huge online customer data by e CRM software after the Internet was born. Companies could update the data of customer needs and obtain the priorities of their experience. This led to first clickable banner ad being going live in 1994, which was the "You Will" campaign by

AT&T and over first four months of it going live, 44% of all people who saw it clicked on the ad.

In the 2000s, with more and more Internet users and the birth of iPhone, customers started searching products and making decisions about their needs online first, instead of consulting salesperson, which created a new problem for the marketing department of a company. In addition, survey in 2000 in the United Kingdom found that most retailers had not registered their own domain address. These problems made marketers find the digital ways for market development.

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In 2007, the concept of marketing automation was raised to solve the problem above. Marketing automation helped companies' segment customers, launch multichannel marketing campaigns and provide personalized information for customers. However, the speed of its adaptability to consumer devices was not fast enough.

Digital marketing became more sophisticated in the 2000s and the 2010s, when the proliferation of devices' capable of accessing digital media led to sudden growth. Statistics produced in 2012 and 2013 showed that digital marketing was still growing. With development of social media in the 2000s, such as LinkedIn, Face book, YouTube and Twitter, consumers became highly dependent on digital electronics in daily lives. They expected seamless user experience across different channels for searching product's information. The change of customer behavior improved the diversification of marketing technology. Worldwide digital marketing has become the most common term, especially after the year 2013. Digital media growth was estimated at 4.5 trillion online ads served annually with digital media spend at 48% growth in 2010. An increasing portion of advertising stems from businesses employing Online Behavioral Advertising (OBA) to tailor advertising for internet users, but OBA raises concern of consumer privacy and data protection.

III. Digital Marketing Tactics and Examples:

Digital marketers are in charge of driving **brand awareness** and **lead generation** through all the digital channels -- both free and paid -- at company's disposal. These channels include social media, the company's own website, search engine rankings, email, display advertising, and the company's blog. The digital marketer focuses on different key performance indicator (KPI) for each channel so they can properly measure the company's performance across each one. Digital marketing is carried out across many marketing roles today. In small companies, one generalist might own many of the digital marketing tactics described above at the same time. In larger companies, these tactics have multiple specialists that each focus on just one or two of the brand's digital channels. Here are some examples of these specialists:

The best digital marketers have clear picture of how each digital marketing campaign supports their overarching goals. And depending on goals of their marketing strategy, marketers can support larger campaign through free and paid channels at their disposal. A **content marketer**, for example, can create series of blog posts that serve to generate leads from a new eBook the business recently created. The company's **social media marketer** might then help promote these blog posts through paid and organic posts on the business's social media accounts. Perhaps the **email marketer** creates an email campaign to send those who download the eBook more information on company. Following are some of most common digital marketing tactics and the channels involved-

- **Search Engine Optimization (SEO):** This is process of optimizing website to "rank" higher in search engine results pages, thereby increasing the amount of organic (or free) traffic your website receives. The channels that benefit from SEO include Websites, Blogs, and Info graphics.
- **Social Media Marketing:** This practice promotes your brand and your content on social media channels to increase brand awareness, drive traffic, and generate leads for your business. The channels you can use in social media marketing include Face book, Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram, Snap chat, Pinterest, and Google+.
- **Content Marketing:** It denotes the creation and promotion of content assets for the purpose of generating brand awareness, traffic growth, lead generation, and customers. The channels that can play a part in your content marketing strategy include Blog posts, EBooks and whitepapers, Info graphics, Online brochures and look books.
- **Affiliate Marketing:** This is a type of performance-based advertising where you receive commission for promoting someone else's products, services on your website. Affiliate marketing channels include Hosting video ads through the YouTube Partner Program and Posting affiliate links from your social media accounts.
- **Native Advertising :** Native advertising refers to advertisements that are primarily content-led and featured on a platform alongside other, non-paid content. Buzz Feed-sponsored posts are a good example, but many people also consider social media advertising to be "native" – Face book advertising and Instagram advertising.
- **Marketing Automation:** Marketing automation refers to the software that serves to automate your basic marketing operations. Many marketing departments can automate repetitive tasks they would otherwise do manually, such as Email newsletters, Social media post scheduling, Contact list updating, Lead-nurturing workflows, Campaign tracking and reporting.
- **Pay-Per-Click (PPC):** PPC is a method of driving traffic to your website by paying a publisher every time your ad is clicked. One of the most common types of PPC is Google Ad Words, which allows you to pay for top slots on Google's search engine results pages at a price "per click" of the links you place. Other channels where you

can use PPC mainly include Paid ads on Face book, Promoted Tweets on Twitter, Sponsored Messages on LinkedIn.

- **Email Marketing:** Companies use email marketing as a way of communicating with their audiences. Email is often used to promote content, discounts and events, as well as to direct people toward the business's website. The types of emails you might send in an email marketing campaign include Blog subscription newsletters, Follow-up emails to website visitors who downloaded something, Customer welcome emails, Holiday promotions to loyalty program members, Tips or similar series emails for customer nurturing.
- **Inbound Marketing:** Inbound marketing refers to the "full-funnel" approach to attracting, engaging, and delighting customers using online content. You can use every digital marketing tactic listed above throughout an inbound marketing strategy.
- **Online PR:** Online PR is practice of securing earned online coverage with digital publications, blogs, and other content-based websites. It's much like traditional PR, but in the online space. The channels you can use to maximize your PR efforts include: Reporter outreach via social media Engaging online reviews of your company, Engaging comments on your personal website or blog.

IV. Digital Marketing – a boost to today's businesses:

Regardless of what your company sells, digital marketing still involves building out buyer's personas to identify your audience's needs and creating valuable online content.

- **B2B Digital Marketing:**
If company is business-to-business (B2B), digital marketing efforts are likely to be centered on online lead generation, with end goal being for someone to speak to salesperson. The role of your marketing strategy is to attract and convert highest quality leads for salespeople via your website and supporting digital channels. Beyond website, you'll probably choose to focus efforts on business-focused channels like LinkedIn where your demographic is spending their time online.
- **B2C Digital Marketing:**
If your company is business-to-consumer (B2C), depending on price point of products, the goal of digital marketing efforts is to attract people to website and have they become customers without ever needing to speak to salesperson. For that reason, you're probably less likely to focus on 'leads' in their traditional sense, and more likely to focus on building an accelerated buyer's journey, from the moment someone lands on your website, to moment that they make a purchase. This will often mean your product features in your content higher up in the marketing funnel than it might for a B2B business, and you might need to use stronger calls-to-action (CTAs). For B2C companies, channels like Instagram and Pinterest are more valuable than business-focused platforms LinkedIn.

➤ **Website Traffic:**

You can see the exact number of people who have viewed your website's homepage in real time by using digital analytics software, available in marketing platforms like Hub Spot. Also how many pages they visited, what device they were using, and where they came from, amongst other digital analytics data. This intelligence helps you to prioritize which marketing channels to spend more or less time on, based on the number of people those channels are driving to your website. For example, if only 10% of your traffic is coming from organic search, you know that you probably need to spend some time on SEO to increase that percentage.

➤ **Content Performance and Lead Generation:**

Imagine you've created product brochure and posted it through people's letterboxes -- that brochure is a form of content, albeit offline. The problem is no idea how many people opened your brochure or how many people threw it straight into trash.

➤ **Attribution Modeling:**

An effective digital marketing strategy combined with right tools and technologies allows to trace all sales back to customer's first digital touch point with your business is called attribution modeling. It allows identifying trends in the way people research and buying your product, helping you to make more informed decisions about what parts of your marketing strategy deserve more attention, and what parts of your sales cycle need refining. *Connecting the dots between marketing and sales is hugely important -- according to Aberdeen Group, companies with strong sales and marketing alignment achieve a 20% annual growth rate, compared to a 4% decline in revenue for companies with poor alignment. If you can improve your customer's journey through the buying cycle by using digital technologies, then it's likely to reflect positively on your business's bottom line.*

- **Online behavioral advertising:** is the practice of collecting information about a user's online activity over time, "on a particular device and across different, unrelated websites, in order to deliver advertisements tailored to that user's interests and preferences.

- **Collaborative Environment:** A collaborative environment can be set up between the organization, technology service provider, and digital agencies to optimize effort, resource sharing, reusability and communications. Organizations are inviting their customers to help them better understand how to service them. Much of this is acquired via company websites where the organization invites people to share ideas that are then evaluated by other users of the site. Using this method of acquiring data and developing new products can foster the organizations relationship with their customer as well as spawn ideas that would otherwise be overlooked.

- **Data-driven advertising:** Users generate lot of data in every step they take on the path of customer journey and Brands can now use that data to activate their known audience with data-driven programmatic media

buying. Without exposing customers' privacy, users' Data can be collected from digital channels (e.g.: when customer visits a website, reads an e-mail, or launches and interact with brand's mobile app), brands can also collect data from real world customer interactions, such as brick and mortar stores visits and from CRM and Sales engines datasets. Data-driven advertising is empowering brands to find their loyal customers in their audience and deliver in real time much more personal communication, highly relevant to each customer's moment and actions.

- **Remarketing:** Remarketing plays a major role in digital marketing. This tactic allows marketers to publish targeted ads in front of an interest category or defined audiences, generally called searchers in web speak, they have either searched for particular products or services or visited a website for some purpose.
- **Game advertising:** Game ads are advertisements that exist within computer or video games. One of the most common examples of in-game advertising is billboards appearing in sports games. In-game ads also might appear as brand-name products like guns, cars, or clothing that exist as gaming status symbols.
- **Ease of access:** A key objective is engaging digital marketing customers and allowing them to interact with brand through servicing and delivery of digital media. Users with access to Internet can use many digital mediums, such as Face book, YouTube, Forums, and Email etc. Through Digital communications it creates a multi-communication channel where information can be quickly shared around world by anyone without any regard to who they are.

V. How the effectiveness of Digital Marketing Campaigns is measured?

The evaluation criteria and metrics for the digital marketing campaigns classified according to its type and time span. Regarding the type, either evaluate campaigns "Quantitatively" or "Qualitatively". Quantitative metrics may include "Sales Volume" and "Revenue Increase/Decrease". While qualitative metrics may include enhanced "Brand awareness, image and health" as well as "relationship with the customers".

Shifting the focus to time span, we may need to measure some "Interim Metrics", which give us some insight during journey itself, as well as we need to measure some "Final Metrics" at the end of journey to inform use if overall initiative was successful or not. For example, most social media metrics and indicators such as likes, shares and engagement comments may be classified as interim metrics while final increase/decrease in sales volume is clearly from final category. The correlation between these categories should exist. Otherwise, disappointing results may happen at the end.

Below are some aspects that need to be considered to have an effective digital media campaign:

1. Interesting mail titles differentiate one advertisement from the other. This separates advertisements from the clutter. **2. Establishment of customer exclusivity:** A list of

customers and customer's details should be kept on database for follow up and selected customers can be sent selected offers and promotions of deals related to customer's previous buyer behavior. **3. Low Technical Requirements:** In order to get full use out of digital marketing it is useful to make you advertising campaigns have low technical requirements. **4. Rewards:** The lucrative offers would always help in making your digital campaign a success. Give some reward at end of campaign.

VI. Pros and Cons of Digital Marketing:

Digital marketing allows marketers to see accurate results in real time. If an advert is put in newspaper, it is difficult to estimate how many people actually flipped to that page and paid attention to ad. There's no surefire way to know if that ad was responsible for any sales at all. Yet digital marketing would help you to know reach for your product/service, to get engaged with prospective customers, to have global reach, to promote in personalized manner. However, with digital marketing have some setbacks. Digital marketing is highly dependent on the internet. Because internet may not be accessible in certain areas or consumers may have poor internet connection. It has lot of clutter, so marketers find it hard to make their advertisements stand out, and get consumers to start conversations about an organizations brand image or products. But still large amount of competing goods and services that are also using same digital marketing strategies can be the disadvantage. Some companies can be portrayed by customers negatively as some consumers lack trust online due to the amount of advertising that appears on websites and social media that can be considered frauds. Even an individual or small group of people can harm image of an established brand. Digital marketing disseminates only information to prospects most of whom do not have purchasing authority/power. Hence reflection of digital marketing into real sales volume is skeptical.

VII. A light on Real cases under Digital marketing:

1. Every Smile Matters: Britannia Good Day supports children born with cleft lip

On World Smiles Day, October 5th, Britannia Good Day launched the Every Smile Matters campaign. The campaign focuses on very important aspect that in today's day and age, smiles have been taken for granted and we don't smile enough. Good Day, has partnered with Smile Train India, the world's leading cleft charity that provides free cleft surgery and care to children. According to a Smile Train study, 1 in 1,000 Indian children are born with a cleft lip –common birth condition that can occur alone or as part of genetic condition or syndrome. Not only does this condition prohibit smiling, it can also cause difficulty in natural activities such as eating and speaking.

2. Parle Kismi spreads love this Valentine's Day in collaboration with the dabbawalas

The Har Kismi Mein Hai Kiss campaign by Parle Kismi is an attempt to spread some love on Valentine's Day by dropping in a reminder to consumers with the help of their dabbawalas. Working professionals often forget Valentine's Day and Parle Kismi wanted to send out a sweet reminder to consumers to wish their partners in time. 'Food is way to one's heart' so Parle collaborated with the most

successful food delivery system – The Dabbawalas. They made pouch of love that consisted of Kismi paan toffees - new variant of Kismi and a reminder note asking them to express love to their loved ones this Valentine's. This pouch was attached to each dabba and was received by almost one lakh people. This simple act by Parle Kismi brought joy to lives of many couples in Mumbai. Parle Kismi has always stood as an enabler and bringing about small moments of happiness in lives of its consumers. This campaign was an extension of the thought for Valentine's Day.

3. HDFC Ergo markets its new app with "Ab Take It Easy":

Ab Take It Easy practices what it preaches, reassuring policyholders that in case of health emergency, first and foremost priority should be you, not formalities with health insurance. Depicting the panic induced jitters that one experiences during the 'moment of truth', wherein the focus of family and friends should be immediate attention to the patient, HDFC Ergo Health Insurance debuted their new, smart phone apps with Ab Take It Easy, which helps put policyholders first, formalities second. Explained through a vigilant father's regular preparation drill whenever he hears ambulance sirens in distance, Ab Take It Easy shows us how his worry is laid to rest knowing that all his health insurance details, and location of nearest cashless hospital are available in moment.

VIII. Conclusion:

To summarize, digital marketing has a bright future for long term sustainability of the product or services in the current technological market with all its pros and cons.

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